

A Comparison of the Efficacy of Pitfall and Vacuum Sampling in the Collection of Spiders (Araneae) in Grassland Environments – Supplementary material

Table S1. Spider species catch totals for pitfall trapping and vacuum sampling.

Spider Taxa	Pitfall	Vacuum	Global Totals
<i>Clubionidae</i>			
<i>Clubiona diversa</i>	0	2	2
<i>Clubiona stagnatilis</i>	1	3	4
<i>Clubiona terrestris</i>	1	2	3
<i>Hahnidae</i>			
<i>Cicurina cicur</i>	1	0	1
<i>Iberina montana</i>	0	12	12
<i>Linyphiidae</i>			
<i>Agyneta rurestris</i>	2	17	19
<i>Bathyphantes gracilis</i>	63	292	355
<i>Centromerita bicolor</i>	5	2	7
<i>Centromerita concinna</i>	36	26	62
<i>Centromerus dilutus</i>	0	35	35
<i>Ceratinella brevipes</i>	0	8	8
<i>Cnephalocotes obscurus</i>	0	24	24
<i>Diplocephalus picinus</i>	1	5	6
<i>Erigone atra</i>	31	109	140
<i>Erigone dentipalpis</i>	16	47	63
<i>Gnathonarium dentatum</i>	4	24	28
<i>Gonatium rubens</i>	7	15	22
<i>Kaestneria pullata</i>	0	2	2
<i>Maso sundevalli</i>	2	11	13
<i>Micrargus herbigradus</i>	0	16	16
<i>Monocephalus fuiscipes</i>	2	2	4
<i>Neriene clathrata</i>	5	16	21
<i>Oedothorax fuscus</i>	94	75	169

<i>Oedothorax retusus</i>	42	16	58
<i>Palliduphantes ericaeus</i>	2	151	153
<i>Pelecopsis parallela</i>	2	31	33
<i>Pocadicnemis pumilla</i>	0	4	4
<i>Stemonyphantes lineatus</i>	0	2	2
<i>Tallusia experta</i>	2	3	5
<i>Tapioncyba mitis</i>	2	0	2
<i>Tapinocyba praecox</i>	6	2	8
<i>Tenuiphantes cristatus</i>	0	4	4
<i>Tenuiphantes flavipes</i>	3	8	11
<i>Tenuiphantes mengei</i>	17	51	68
<i>Tenuiphantes tenuis</i>	64	186	250
<i>Tenuiphantes zimmermanni</i>	9	26	35
<i>Walckenaeria antica</i>	4	3	7
<i>Walckenaeria cuspidata</i>	0	2	2
<i>Wiehlea calcarifera</i>	1	0	1
<i>Liocranidae</i>			
<i>Agroeca proxima</i>	7	1	8
<i>Lycosidae</i>			
<i>Pardosa nigriceps</i>	1	6	7
<i>Pardosa pullata</i>	6	10	16
<i>Pardosa tenuipes</i>	1	1	2
<i>Trochosa terricola</i>	11	0	11
<i>Mimetidae</i>			
<i>Ero cambridgei</i>	0	5	5
<i>Ero furcata</i>	1	6	7
<i>Tetragnathidae</i>			
<i>Pachygnatha clercki</i>	1	3	4
<i>Pachygnatha degeeri</i>	16	32	48
<i>Theridiidae</i>			
<i>Enoplognatha thoracica</i>	0	1	1
<i>Thomisidae</i>			

<i>Ozyptila atomaria</i>	2	12	14
<i>Xysticus cristatus</i>	3	5	8
Totals	474	1316	1790

Table S2. Bycatch order catch totals for pitfall trapping and vacuum sampling.

Bycatch Order	Pitfall	Vacuum	Global totals
Opisthoptora	136	0	136
Coleoptera	441	741	1182
Stylommatophora	593	6	599
Opiliones	67	68	135
Hemiptera	101	667	768
Hymenoptera	383	758	1141
Diptera	640	1673	2313
Isopoda	45	110	155
Amphipoda	77	4	81
Lepidoptera	10	79	89
Myriapoda	20	4	24
Archaeognatha	3	43	46
Dermaptera	7	5	12
Pseudoscorpiones	1	3	4
Immature Araneae	200	1989	2189
Urodela	2	0	2
Totals	2726	6150	8876

S3. Study Site locations

Site	Sample Point	Technique
Helman NR	T1	Pitfall
Helman NR	T2	Pitfall
Helman NR	T3	Pitfall
Helman NR	T4	Pitfall
Helman NR	T5	Pitfall
Helman NR	T6	Pitfall
Helman NR	T7	Pitfall
Helman NR	T8	Pitfall
Helman NR	T9	Pitfall
Helman NR	T10	Pitfall
Goss NNR	T11	Pitfall
Goss NNR	T12	Pitfall
Goss NNR	T13	Pitfall
Goss NNR	T14	Pitfall
Goss NNR	T15	Pitfall
Goss NNR	T16	Pitfall
Goss NNR	T17	Pitfall
Goss NNR	T18	Pitfall
Goss NNR	T19	Pitfall
Goss NNR	T20	Pitfall
Helman NR	V1	Vacuum
Helman NR	V2	Vacuum
Helman NR	V3	Vacuum
Helman NR	V4	Vacuum
Helman NR	V5	Vacuum
Helman NR	V6	Vacuum
Helman NR	V7	Vacuum
Helman NR	V8	Vacuum

Helman NR	V9	Vacuum
Helman NR	V10	Vacuum
Goss NNR	V11	Vacuum
Goss NNR	V12	Vacuum
Goss NNR	V13	Vacuum
Goss NNR	V14	Vacuum
Goss NNR	V15	Vacuum
Goss NNR	V16	Vacuum
Goss NNR	V17	Vacuum
Goss NNR	V18	Vacuum
Goss NNR	V19	Vacuum
Goss NNR	V20	Vacuum

Figure S1. Compartment G1, Goss Moor NNR.

Figure S2. Compartment G2, Goss Moor NNR.

Figure S3. Compartment G3, Goss Moor NNR.

Figure S4. Compartment H1, H2 & H3, Helman Tor NR.

Figure S5. Compartment H4, Helman Tor NR.

S4. Comparison of sample points.

Figure S6. Rank spider abundance at each sample point n=5. Pitfall traps (T), Vacuum samples (V).

Figure S7. Rank spider richness at each sample point n=5. Pitfall traps (T), Vacuum samples (V).

Figure S8. Rank bycatch abundance at each sample point n=5. Pitfall traps (T), Vacuum samples (V).

Figure S9. Bycatch richness at each sample point n=5. Pitfall traps (T), Vacuum samples (V).

(Original instructions)

ENGLISH

Protecting the environment

Separate collection. This product must not be disposed of with normal household waste.

Should you find one day that your Black & Decker product needs replacement, or if it is of no further use to you, do not dispose of it with household waste. Make this product available for separate collection.

Separate collection of used products and packaging allows materials to be recycled and used again. Re-use of recycled materials helps prevent environmental pollution and reduces the demand for raw materials.

Local regulations may provide for separate collection of electrical products from the household, at municipal waste sites or by the retailer when you purchase a new product.

Black & Decker provides a facility for the collection and recycling of Black & Decker products once they have reached the end of their working life. To take advantage of this service please return your product to any authorised repair agent who will collect them on our behalf.

You can check the location of your nearest authorised repair agent by contacting your local Black & Decker office at the address indicated in this manual. Alternatively, a list of authorised Black & Decker repair agents and full details of our after-sales service and contacts are available on the Internet at: www.2helpU.com

Batteries

At the end of their useful life, discard batteries with due care for our environment:

- ◆ Run the battery down completely, then remove it from the tool.
- ◆ NiCd, NiMH and Li-Ion batteries are recyclable. Place the battery(s) in a suitable packaging to ensure that the terminals cannot be short-circuited. Take them to any authorised repair agent or a local recycling station.
- ◆ Do not short-circuit the battery terminals.
- ◆ Do not dispose of the battery(s) in a fire as this may result in a risk of personal injury or an Explosion.

Technical data

		GWC3600L (H1)
Voltage	V _{dc}	36
No Load Speed	RPM	12700
Air Volume	m ³ /min	3.46
Weight (blower)	kg	1.72
Weight (Vacuum)	kg	2.42
Battery		BL1336
Voltage	V _{DC}	36
Capacity	Ah	1.3
Type		Li-Ion
Charger		905673** (typ. 1)
Input voltage	V _{AC}	230
Output voltage	V _{DC}	36
Current	mA	1300

Hand/Arm weighted vibration value according to EN 60745:

Vibration emission value (a_h) < 2.5 m/s², uncertainty (K) 1.5 m/s²

L_{pA} (measure sound pressure) 81 dB(A), Uncertainty = 3 dB(A)

L_{WA} (guaranteed sound power) 95 dB(A), Uncertainty = 3 dB(A)